

Problems of Organizing Internal Evaluation in Schools in the Educational Context of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *For the economic growth of the country, students need not only proper education in school, but also monitoring and evaluation in education. From this point of view, in this article, whether there is a need to improve the system of internal monitoring in schools or not, gaps in the organization of school monitoring were studied. In the study, a questionnaire was conducted with the participation of 106 respondents, consisting of school principals and candidates. The results of the survey were analyzed using the mathematical-statistical analysis method. Uzbekistan education in the context of it was determined that there is a need to improve the system of internal monitoring of the quality of education in schools, there is a need for independent evaluation and monitoring organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools and create a road map for their individual development.*

Key words: *quality of education, assessment, internal monitoring, directors, personalized development map.*

Introduction

For the economic growth of the country, students need not only proper education in school, but also assessment and monitoring in education. In fact, the evaluation of students' knowledge and skills in school education, as well as the identification and monitoring of existing achievements and shortcomings in education, increases efficiency and develops human capital in the country.

Organization, control, and management of the educational process at school require specific scientific approaches. In particular, principles such as reliability, independence, systematicity, and complexity are followed in the management of the quality of education. Attestation, accreditation and internal monitoring tests are of particular importance. As above mentioned, since education is a multi-component process, the factors affecting education are always identified and existing gaps are filled. Monitoring is an important tool for determining the quality of school education.

Literature review

Improving the internal monitoring system for the quality of education in schools is an important and integral part of the modern educational process. Scientific literature and sources were analyzed to get deeper information on the uniqueness, relevance and practices of this process. In this regard it was studied separately in the scientific-methodical works of a number of scientists. Including by AJ Shinkfield in the manual monitoring in education and evaluation system different models including the CIPP model (Context, Input, Process, Product) and of monitoring stages about in detail will stop. (Shinkfield , 2007) Other one in the manual at school internal monitoring organize reach for practical recommendations is given and evaluation results how by doing education quality to improve help to give open is given (Fitzpatrick, 2012) Also another one in the manual in education the news done

increase and to them how resistances to be possible about stopping and in education changes observation and monitoring them basics open is given (Fullan, 2015) That's it Hopkins Scientific in line in his pamphlet school in education in class students activity monitoring , teachers by note to be done results and evaluation systems improvement basics statement will be done . (Hopkins, 2014).

In the local literature, it is stated that in the internal monitoring of the quality of education at the school, the educational achievements of the students, the effectiveness of the school leadership and teachers, the educational environment in the family and at the school are determined and evaluated. (Abdurahim, 2024)

In general, in internal monitoring, it is determined that the factors that lead to a decrease in the quality of education in the school are related to the academic skills of the teacher or the educational environment in the family, or the conditions created in the school, or the management activities of the school management. Measures will be taken to eliminate existing problems.

Research methodology

To determine whether there is a need to improve the internal monitoring system in schools, a number of hypotheses have been determined. In particular, the current state of internal monitoring of the quality of education in schools, whether there is a need for guidelines on the organization of internal monitoring, what problems there are in the organization of internal monitoring in schools, and whether there is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring of the quality of education in schools. to determine that After that, the students of the Management training course organized at the National Institute of Pedagogical Skills named after Abdulla Avloni were selected as participants of the experiment. A survey was conducted with the participation of students of the management training course.

<https://docs.google.com> platform was used to create the questionnaire . HYPERLINK "https://docs.google.com" 106 respondents, including current school principals and candidates, took part in the survey . Before organizing the process, the purpose of the questionnaire and the procedure for filling it out were explained in detail. It was emphasized that they answered the questions objectively. In order to control those who filled out the questionnaire independently, they answered the questions in groups in the audience under supervision. Then the survey results were analyzed using the mathematical-statistical analysis method .

Discussion and results

determine the periodicity of internal monitoring of the quality of education at the school . The respondents answered the question as follows. (See Figure 1.)

Maktabingizda ta'lim sifati bo'yicha ichki monitoring bir o'quv yilida necha marotaba o'tkaziladi?
106 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 1. Periodicity of internal monitoring in the school

The result of the survey shows that in 67.9% of schools, quarterly internal monitoring is organized regularly. In 18.9 percent, internal monitoring is organized twice a year. About 4 percent of schools conduct internal monitoring tests only once a year.

So, it seems that internal monitoring is being organized at a certain level in all schools. Basically, internal monitoring tests are organized once every quarter.

Determine when the internal monitoring of the quality of education will be carried out at the school . The respondents answered the question as follows. (See Figure 2.)

Maktabingizda ichki monitoring sinovlarini qachon tashkil etasiz?

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Figure 2. Internal monitoring time at the school

The results of the survey show that in 59.4% of schools, monitoring tests are organized after classes on school days. In 36.8 percent, internal monitoring is organized during classes. Almost 4 percent of respondents noted that internal monitoring is organized on holidays and weekends.

It seems that in more than 40% of schools, internal monitoring is organized during classes, on weekends and during vacations without following the norms.

Respondents answered the following questions in the survey to determine whether there is a need for internal monitoring in the school . (See Figure 3.)

Maktabda ichki monitoringni o'tkazishning batafsil tartibi aks etgan yo'riqnoma mavjudmi?

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Figure 3. There is a need for guidelines for conducting internal monitoring in the school

The results of the survey show that 30.2% of schools do not have instructions that reflect the detailed procedure for organizing monitoring, organizers conduct internal monitoring based on their existing experience. 46.2% of the respondents stated that it is available and noted that they always use it. 20.8 percent of participants noted that there is an existing, but not detailed procedure.

Therefore, the results of the survey show that there is a need for excellent guidelines for the organization of internal monitoring in schools.

After that, to the question asked in order to determine what problems exist in the organization of internal monitoring in the school, the respondents wrote that there are various problems. (See Figure 4.)

Maktabda baholash va ichki monitoringni tashkil etishda qanday muammolar bor :

106 ответов

Test va so'rovnomalar bankini yaratishda
Тестларда муоммо йуктест ва диктантлар
Sharoitlar yetishmasligi
Муаммо йўқ
Муаммо кўп холис шаффоф ўтказиш қийин ўқитувчиларга ён босиш ҳолати материалларни тайёрлаш талаб даражасида бўлмайди
Umumiy tizim yaratish kerak
АКТ
Testlar bazasi

Figure 4. Internal monitoring is available at the school

problems

The result of the survey shows that there are mainly the following problems in the organization of internal monitoring in the school:

- *m books contingent high therefore time , place and resources lack of*
- *interests collision high the fact that*
- *material technical base enough level that it is not ;*
- *monitoring results check long it takes time and to this personnel lack of*
- *monitoring of teachers according to knowledge and skills lack of*
- *conducting internal monitoring periodicity study process to the basket not included ;*
- *study year during many (four and from him many times transfer ;*
- *parents neglect and irresponsibility ;*
- *high education institutions and centers with cooperation there is that it is not ;*
- *manual and methodical instructions there is that it is not ;*
- *conducting internal monitoring process not digitized ;*
- *during internal monitoring to transparency attention not to focus ;*
- *assignments and questionnaire bank there is that it is not*

Therefore, there are a number of problems in terms of content, organizational and methodical support and training of personnel in connection with the organization of internal monitoring in schools.

At the end of the research questionnaire, the respondents answered the following question to determine whether there is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools . (See Figure 5.)

Maktablarda ichki monitoringni o'tkazib beradigan mustaqil nodavlat tashkilotlarga ehtiyoj bormi?
106 ОТВЕТОВ

Figure 5. There is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools

The result of the survey shows that 50% of the respondents stated that there is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools, while the other half noted that there is no need for such an organization.

Therefore, it can be said that there is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools.

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the results of the research, the following **conclusions** can be drawn:

first of all there is a need to improve the system of internal monitoring of the quality of education in schools . Because internal monitoring of the quality of education in schools is organized once a quarter and almost 40% of schools do not follow the standards: during classes, on weekends, and even during vacations.

secondly, there are a number of problems related to substantive, organizational and methodological support and personnel training in the field of internal monitoring in schools.

thirdly, there is a need for excellent guidelines, methodological manuals and guidelines for internal school monitoring.

fourthly, there is a need for independent non-governmental organizations that conduct internal monitoring in schools and create a road map for their individual development.

In order to improve the system of internal monitoring in schools, the following **is suggested**:

- *for internal monitoring to be conducted transparently, objectively and consistently, the procedure for conducting it is determined in the curriculum and time standards;*
- *take steps to digitize the internal monitoring process, create a bank of tasks and questionnaires;*
- *schools higher education institutions and centers with partners strengthen*
- *conducting internal monitoring in schools order reflection reached manual and methodical instructions and guidelines prepared publication to do*
- *high education institutions and qualification increase in the centers student and monitoring of teachers according to knowledge and skills systematic development practice to the road to put*

- *it is necessary to take measures to open non-state evaluation centers that conduct internal monitoring in schools and create a road map for individual development of schools.*

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